

HRM PRACTICES, WORK ENGAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTION

MADA T.M, YUPITER G*

Lecturer and Senior Researcher, Trisakti School of Management, Faculty of Management, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: madatrimajaya@gmail.com, yupiter@stietrisakti.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to determine the impact of employee satisfaction with human resource management (HRM) practices (training satisfaction, performance appraisal satisfaction, and pay satisfaction) on work engagement and turnover intention of employees of Sygma Exa Grafika. In addition, the mediating role of work engagement between employee satisfaction with HRM practices and turnover intention is also assessed. In this study, the data used came from questionnaires distributed to respondents using likert scale measurement and collected respondents from a total of 123 employees who receive training, performance appraisal, and pay. The sampling technique used in this study is saturated sampling. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) is used as data analysis method. The results of this study state that training satisfaction and pay satisfaction each have an effect on work engagement. However, performance appraisal satisfaction has no effect on work engagement. Furthermore, work engagement mediates the relationship between training satisfaction, pay satisfaction and turnover intention. However, it did not have any mediating effect on performance appraisal satisfaction and turnover intention.

Keywords: HRM Practices, Training Satisfaction, Performance Appraisal Satisfaction, Pay Satisfaction, Work Engagement, Turnover Intention.

INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing industry has experienced a decline due to the pandemic that has lasted for the past two years. Despite the sharp decline in the first quarter of 2022, there are still several types of industries that experienced an increase in production. The types of industries that experienced an increase in production were the Printing & Recording Media Reproduction Industry by 49.45 percent, the Non-Metal Mineral Industry by 16.52 percent, and the Food Industry by 15.83 percent and the Beverage Industry by 4.59 percent (DKISP, 2022). The printing industry is part of the manufacturing industry sector. The printing industry is constantly changing at a rapid pace. Digital printing and digital transformation are trends accelerated by the pandemic and will persist into the future. The world of printing, especially the commercial sector, has been hit quite hard during the pandemic. But within the industry, some experts say that 2022 will be a year of revival and turnaround.

Table 1: Employees of Sygma Group

Entity	2020			2021			2022		
	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women	Total
Madina	4	5	9	5	6	11	3	7	10
Sygma Daya Insani	40	14	54	42	16	58	36	13	49
Sygma Examedia Arkanleema	64	16	80	81	25	106	83	28	111
Sygma Exa Grafika	162	60	222	181	62	243	93	30	123
Sygma Media Innovation	35	8	43	37	7	44	28	9	37

Source: Internal data of Sygma Group

The success or failure of a company largely depends on its human resources. The role of human resources is not only about hiring people in an organization, but also about retaining them (Irabor and Okolie, 2019). The topic of voluntary rotation has been extensively studied over the past few decades. Empirical evidence shows that high voluntary turnover rates are detrimental to organizations because they have a negative impact on organizational effectiveness and success (Shaw, 2011).

According to Purwito in Soegandhi (2013), the level of employee turnover can be categorized as high if it reaches 2% and above. Based on data obtained from Human Capital of Sygma Group, data on the number of employees and employee turnover for the 2020-2022 period are as follows in table 1.

From the table 1, it can be seen that most of the employees from Sygma Group are spread across Sygma Exa Grafika, which has a total of 123 people and Sygma Examedia Arkanleema, which has a total of 111 people. And the remaining small portion is spread across other entities such as Madina, Sygma Daya Insani, and Sygma Media Innovation. It can also be seen that there are fluctuations in the number of employees from year to year, such as the increase in the number of employees from the previous year, as happened at Sygma Examedia Arkanleema and vice versa, there was a decrease in the number of employees in other entities.

Table 2: Employees Turnover of Sygma Group

Entiy	Employee Leave			Turnover Rate	
	2020	2021	2022	2021	2022
Madina	4	4	1	40%	10%
Sygma Daya Insani	8	2	1	3,57%	1,87%
Sygma Examedia Arkanleema	9	17	8	18,27%	7,37%
Sygma Exa Grafika	21	1	4	0,43%	2,18%
Sygma Media Innovation	4	3	2	6,90%	4,93%

Source: Internal data of Sygma Group

From these data it can be seen that the employee turnover rate for each Sygma Group entity in recent years has been relatively high in several companies such as in Madina which reached 10%, Sygma Examedia Arkanleema 7.37%, Sygma Media Innovation 4.93%, and Sygma Exa Grafika 2.18%. More specifically Sygma Exa Grafika which has the largest number of employees, the employee turnover rate continues to increase compared to other entities.

Turnover can be advantageous when a worker who isn't productive quits, for example. This gives other people with better abilities the chance to get employed or promoted (Ketkaew et al., 2020). High turnover intention can indicate that the company is ineffective, reduce efficiency and productivity so that it can endanger the company, in the end the company loses employees who have previous experience and need to train new employees (Joarder et al., 2011).

Based on previous research performed by Memon et al. (2020) about the effect of training satisfaction, pay satisfaction, performance appraisal satisfaction, and work engagement on turnover intention state that training satisfaction and performance appraisal satisfaction are the two main drivers of employee engagement in the workplace. Work engagement in turn has a negative impact on employee turnover intentions. In addition, work engagement mediates the relationship between employee satisfaction with HRM practices (i.e. training satisfaction and performance appraisal satisfaction) and intent to turnover. However, it has no mediating effect on pay satisfaction and turnover intention.

On the other hand, previous research conducted by Mumtahanah (2017) which used training satisfaction as the independent variable and turnover intention as the dependent variable as well as work engagement as a mediating variable shows that there is no influence between training satisfaction on employee turnover intention. Then, there is an influence between training satisfaction on work engagement of employees. However, there is no effect of work engagement on employee turnover intention. Also in contrast to research conducted by Sari et al (2021) which stated that training satisfaction influences work engagement and work engagement mediate between training satisfaction and turnover intention.

Another previous study was conducted by Hidayat (2018) which used pay satisfaction as the independent variable and turnover intention as the dependent variable as well as work engagement as a mediating variable shows that pay satisfaction has an effect on turnover intention through work engagement. Meanwhile, research conducted by Memon et al (2020) stated the opposite.

Training Satisfaction

Schmidt (2007) states that training satisfaction is the extent to which people like or dislike the set of planned activities organized to develop the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to effectively perform a given task or job. According to this definition, training satisfaction is defined as how people feel about the aspects of the job training they receive (Schmidt, 2007). Therefore, training satisfaction as a measures the employees' feeling about the whole training activities such as identifying the training needs, designing the training program, delivering training contents, activating learning occurring, and assessing training evaluation (Omar, 2021) in Afriansyah & Widjaja (2021).

Training is especially important for giving employees the tools they need to feel ready to engage fully to their jobs (Gruman & Saks 2019). One's degree of work engagement rises when they have satisfied in their ability to meet expectations on the job. Organizations that offer their employees numerous opportunities for training and development report higher levels of work

engagement (Crawford et al. 2010). If satisfaction with training affects work engagement, and work engagement affects turnover intention, it is plausible that work engagement might mediate the relationship between HRM practices and turnover intention (Memon et al., 2020). JD-R theory describes engagement as a motivational process, implies that it can mediate between job resources and positive workplace outcomes. (Karadas & Karatepe, 2018). Thus, positive experience such as training satisfaction from applied HRM practices serves as a potential source of employment that encourages employee determination and work effort, which translates into positive outcomes like lower turnover intention (Memon et al., 2020).

H₁: There is an influence of training satisfaction toward work engagement.

H₅: There is a mediating effect of work engagement between training satisfaction and turnover intention.

Performance Appraisal Satisfaction

Mount (1984) in Morgan (2000) states that performance appraisal satisfaction is the reaction of employees to various aspects of the appraisal process. According to Giles and Mossholder (1990) in Othman (2014), performance appraisal satisfaction is the extent to which the employee perceives performance ratings reflect those behaviors that contribute to the organization. Performance appraisal satisfaction is defined as a positive reaction of employees towards four dimensions of organizational justice namely distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational justice. (Saraih & Karim, 2017).

Employees believe they have been handled fairly by their employer if they believe the appraisal was impartial, fair, and advantageous to both parties. A sense of obligation is created by such equitable treatment, which the employee acts upon by becoming more engaged at work. In essence, employees' good opinions of the performance appraisal system spur their work engagement (Memon et al., 2019). If performance appraisal satisfaction affects work engagement, and work engagement affects turnover intention, it is reasonable that work engagement mediates the relationship between performance appraisal satisfaction and turnover intention. (Memon et al., 2020).

H₂: There is an influence of performance appraisal satisfaction toward work engagement.

H₆: There is a mediating effect of work engagement between performance appraisal satisfaction and turnover intention.

Pay Satisfaction

Miceli & Lane (1991) in Faulk II (2002) states that pay satisfaction as the amount of overall positive affect (or feelings) individuals have toward pay. According to Lawler (1971) in Das et al. (2017), pay satisfaction or dissatisfaction is a function of the discrepancy between employee's expectation of his/her pay and the pay s/he receives. Furthermore, according to Milkovich (2017), pay satisfaction is a function of the discrepancy between employees' perceptions of how much pay they should receive and how much pay they do receive. If these perceptions are equal, an employee is said to experience pay satisfaction.

Financial compensation is a key work resource that encourages employees to meet their obligations and provide positive outcomes like work engagement. (Schaufeli & Taris 2014). Given the significance of financial compensation for satisfying workers' material demands, pay satisfaction should raise workers' levels of work engagement. (Memon et al., 2020). Another study by Memon et al. (2017) found that the likelihood of employee turnover intention is mediated by work engagement and the level of employee satisfaction with HRM practices such as pay.

H₃: There is an influence of pay satisfaction toward work engagement.

H₇: There is a mediating effect of work engagement between pay satisfaction and turnover intention.

Work Engagement

Bakker & Leiter (2010) states that work engagement is a positive, fulfilling, affective-motivational state of work-related well-being that can be seen as the antipod of job details while getting to the essence of challenging problems. Work engagement is the harnessing of organizational member selves to their work roles' as a way of self-expression in work (Kahn, 1990). According to Seymour & Dupre (2008) work engagement is working collegially to meet organizational goals.

A higher level of work engagement lowers voluntary turnover. Engagement at work results in personally satisfying job-related experiences, good health, and a mentality that is positively connected with diligent, forward-moving work efforts. (Shuck et al., 2014). Bailey et al. (2015) found strong evidence for a link between these constructs when they found a significant negative relationship between employee turnover intentions and work engagement. The outcomes of work are improved, the employee has a favorable view of their employer, and their commitment to the organization increases as a result of these positive experiences and feelings. Positively engaged people typically have higher job satisfaction, feel more devoted to the organization, and have no intentions of leaving the organization (Schaufeli & Salanova, 2008). This means that highly engaged employees are less likely to leave their jobs (Memon et al., 2020).

H₄: There is an influence of work engagement toward turnover intention.

Turnover Intention

Schyns et al. (2007) states that turnover intention represents the employee cognitions about a voluntary leave from the employing organization. Turnover intention is the possibility that an employee quits job prior to a date that is specified. (Hughes et al., 2010). Saeed et al. (2014) defined turnover intention as a plan for the employees to quit the organizations; it is a planned attempt to search for the job outside the organization. Based on this, it can be said that turnover intention is an employee's planned effort to leave his/her work organization and it is highly likely to find work outside his/her organization.

Another theory, The Human Capital Theory sets that education, training and development, and other knowledge have a positive effect on productivity and pay (Zula and Chermack 2007).

According to Rahman et al. (2013) the Human Capital theory, employee productivity can be increased by investing in their education. Therefore, in order to increase their production levels, organizations must invest in the development of their personnel. Education and training, however, may increase workers' employability in the labor market and encourage turnover for better positions, according to the Human Capital Theory. The Human Capital Theory views management's investments in the education, training, and development of its workforce as a key driver of turnover intention factor.

RESEARCH MODEL

Figure 1: Research Model

Description:

- X₁: Training Satisfaction
- X₂: Performance Appraisal Satisfaction
- X₃: Pay Satisfaction
- Y: Work Engagement
- Z: Turnover Intention

RESEARCH METHOD

The form of this research is descriptive and causal. The population in this study was 123 employees who receive training, performance appraisal, and pay at the Sygma Exa Grafika. In determining the sample used by the author in this study, the author used the saturated sampling technique. Data collection for this study used a method by distributing questionnaires by using the Likert measurement scale to respondents. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) is used as a data analysis method. The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of training satisfaction, performance appraisal satisfaction, and pay satisfaction on turnover intention mediated by work engagement.

Operational Definition

Training satisfaction is the extent to which people like or dislike the set of planned activities organized to develop the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to effectively perform a given task or job (Schmidt, 2007). Performance appraisal satisfaction is defined as a positive reaction of employees towards four dimensions of organizational justice namely distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational justice (Saraih & Karim, 2017). Pay satisfaction is a function of the discrepancy between employees' perceptions of how much pay they should receive and how much pay they do receive (Milkovich, 2017). Work engagement is a positive, fulfilling, affective-motivational state of work-related well-being that can be seen as the antipod of job details while getting to the essence of challenging problems (Bakker & Leiter, 2010). Turnover intention is the possibility that an employee quits job prior to a date that is specified (Hughes et al., 2010).

RESEARCH RESULT

The descriptive method in this research is used to describe the respondent's profile based on the data that has been obtained. Description of respondent data in this study consists of gender, age, employment status, education, length of work, job classification, and length of work. There were 93 male respondents (75.6%) and 30 female respondents (24.4%). Thus, there were more male respondents in this study. Then there were 38 respondents aged between 20-24 years (30.9%), 38 respondents aged between 25-29 years (30.9%), 18 respondents aged between 30-34 years (14.6%), Respondents aged between 35-39 years were 17 people (13.8%), and respondents aged between 40-45 years were 12 people (9.8%) From these data respondents with an age range of 20-24 years and 25-29 years old were the most dominant age in this research. It is known that 18 people (14.6%) have working status as Workers with Fixed Time Agreements (PKWT), 48 people (39.0%) have daily worker status, and 57 people have permanent employee status (46.3%). Means that the respondent's status as a permanent employee is the most dominant worker in this study.

Furthermore, respondents with the last education level of junior high school were 6 people (4.9%), high school were 101 people (82.1%), diploma and bachelors were 15 people (12.2%), and 1 master degree. (0.8%). From this data, respondents with the most recent high school education category or equivalent were the most dominant in this study. Furthermore, the number of respondents in the production section was 92 people (74.8%), 18 people in the operational section (14.6%), and 13 people in the finance section (10.6%). From these data, respondents in the most dominant production section in this study. Based on length of work, 3 person or 2.4% worked for 4 months, 4 person or 3.3% worked for 6 months, 1-2 years worked 40 people or 32.5%, 48 people or 39.0% worked 3-4 years, 18 people or 14.6% 5-6 years worked, 6 people or 4.9% worked 7-8 years, 9-10 years worked 4 people or 3.2% and have worked for more than 10 years as many as 4 or 3.2%. From this data, respondents who have worked for 1 to 4 years are the most dominant in this study.

An indicator is considered reliable if it has a correlation value above 0.70. However, in the research at the scale development stage, a loading of 0.50 to 0.60 is still acceptable (Ghozali

2021, 35). The loading factors for each variable indicator in this study were >0.5 , with work engagement having the lowest loading of 0.642 and the highest of 0.846 with an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of 0.591; turnover intention has the smallest loading of 0.692 and the highest of 0.798 with an AVE value of 0.578; training satisfaction has the lowest loading of 0.801 and the highest of 0.883 with an AVE value of 0.734; performance appraisal satisfaction has the lowest loading of 0.596 and the highest of 0.852 with an AVE of 0.518; pay satisfaction has the lowest loading of 0.781 and the highest of 0.861 with an AVE of 0.670. It can be concluded that all the variables used in this study have a high individual reflexive measure.

According to Hair et al. (2017, 115) discriminant validity is the extent to which a construct is truly distinct from other by empirical standards. Discriminant validity of a measurement model with reflective indicators is assessed based on cross-loading measurements with variables. If the construct's correlation with measurement items is greater than other construct measures, this indicates that latent constructs predict the size of their block better than indicators in other blocks (Ghozali 2021, 36). In this study, the correlation of each variable indicator is greater than the correlation of other variable indicators, so it can be concluded that the indicators of each latent variable are more than blocks of other variable indicators. It can be seen that each indicator of the work engagement variable, between the smallest 0.642 and the largest 0.846, is the highest correlation to the work engagement variable compared to the correlation of other variables; the indicator of the variable turnover intention between the smallest 0.692 to the largest 0.798 is the highest correlation to the variable turnover intention compared to the correlation of other variables; the indicator of the training satisfaction variable between the smallest 0.801 to the largest 0.883 is the highest correlation to the training satisfaction variable compared to the correlation of other variables; the indicator of the variable performance appraisal satisfaction between the smallest 0.596 to the largest 0.852 is the highest correlation to the variable performance appraisal satisfaction compared to the correlation of other variables; the indicator of the pay satisfaction variable between the smallest 0.790 to the largest 0.861 is the highest correlation to the pay satisfaction variable compared to the correlation of other variables.

Table 3: Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Work Engagement	0.913	0.928
Turnover Intention	0.817	0.872
Training Satisfaction	0.879	0.917
Performance Appraisal Satisfaction	0.872	0.894
Pay Satisfaction	0.902	0.924

Source: statistical data processing output

Reliability test conducted by PLS (Partial Least Square) can be done by looking at Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. The construct is declared reliable if the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values are above 0.70 (Ghozali, 2021, 37). Based on table 3 above, the variables meet the reliability criteria.

Table 4: R-Square & Prediction Relevance (Q²)

	R-Square	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Work Engagement	0.487	0.282
Turnover Intention	0.143	0.069

Source: statistical data processing output

Based on the table above, the Work Engagement variable can be explained by the variables Training Satisfaction, Performance Appraisal Satisfaction, and Pay Satisfaction with an R-Square value of 48.7%, while the remaining 51.3% is explained by other variables or factors outside of this study. Through the table above, the Turnover Intention variable can be explained by the Work Engagement variable with an R-square value of 14.3%, while the remaining 85.7% is explained by other variables or factors outside this study. So it can be concluded that with an R-Square of more than 33%, the exogenous construct for work engagement is moderate, while the exogenous construct for turnover intention is weak with an R-Square of less than 19%.

The value of Q² is more than 0 then the model has predictive relevance, whereas if it is less than 0 then the model has less predictive relevance. This shows that all indicator models have good relevance to endogenous variables (Ghozali 2021, 74). Based on table 4.10, it shows the Q² results of Work Engagement which has a value > 0. This shows that the indicator model of Work Engagement has good relevance to endogenous variables. While the Q² results from Turnover Intention have a value of <0 which means the model less predictive relevance.

Table 5: Summary of Structural Model

	Org. Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Supported
TS -> WE	0.520	6.101	0.000	YES
PAS -> WE	-0.022	0.266	0.791	NO
PS -> WE	0.334	3.325	0.001	YES
WE -> TOI	0.378	4.568	0.000	YES
TS -> WE -> TOI	0.196	3.421	0.001	YES
PAS -> WE -> TOI	-0.008	0.273	0.785	NO
PS -> WE -> TOI	0.126	2.916	0.004	YES

Source: statistical data processing output

Figure 2: Measurement Model Test Results

Source: statistical data processing output

The results of hypothesis testing based on table above are:

H₁ from the hypothesis test results of the table above shows that there is an effect of training satisfaction on work engagement of employees of Sygma Exa Grafika. Significant influence is shown by the t-value of 6.101 > 1.96; and p-value 0.000 < 0.05. The results of this study are consistent with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state that training satisfaction has a significant effect on work engagement.

H₂ from the hypothesis test results of the table above shows that there is no effect of performance appraisal satisfaction on work engagement of employees of Sygma Exa Grafika, which shown by the t-value of 0.266 < 1.96; and p-value 0.791 > 0.05. The results of this study are not in accordance with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state that performance appraisal satisfaction has a significant effect on work engagement.

H₃ from the hypothesis test results of the table above shows that there is an effect of pay satisfaction on work engagement of employees of Sygma Exa Grafika. Significant influence is shown by the t-value of 3.325 > 1.96; and p-value 0.001 < 0.05. The results of this study are not consistent with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state that pay satisfaction has no effect

on work engagement. However, these results are consistent with research conducted by Hidayat (2018) which states that there is an effect of pay satisfaction on work engagement.

H₄ from the hypothesis test results of the table above shows that there is an effect of work engagement on turnover intention of employees of Sygma Exa Grafika. Significant influence is shown by t-value of $4.568 > 1.96$; and p-value $0.000 < 0.05$. The results of this study are consistent with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state that work engagement has a significant effect on work turnover intention.

H₅ from the hypothesis test results of the table above shows that there is a mediating effect of work engagement between training satisfaction and turnover intention of employees of Sygma Exa Grafika, which shown by the t-value of $3.421 > 1.96$; and p-value $0.001 < 0.05$. The results of this study are consistent with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state that work engagement mediates the relationship between training satisfaction and turnover intention.

H₆ from the hypothesis test results of the table above shows that there is no mediating effect of work engagement between performance appraisal satisfaction and turnover intention of employees of Sygma Exa Grafika, which shown by the t-value of $0.273 < 1.96$; and p-value $0.785 > 0.05$. The results of this study are not consistent with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state that work engagement mediates the relationship between performance appraisal satisfaction and turnover intention.

H₇ from the hypothesis test results of the table above shows that there is a mediating effect of work engagement between pay satisfaction and turnover intention of employees of Sygma Exa Grafika, which shown by the t-value of $2.916 > 1.96$; and p-value $0.004 < 0.05$. The results of this study are not consistent with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state work engagement did not mediate the relationship between pay satisfaction and turnover intention. However, these results are consistent with research conducted by Hidayat (2018) which states that work engagement mediates the relationship between pay satisfaction and turnover intention.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that training satisfaction and pay satisfaction each have an effect on work engagement. The results of this study are consistent with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state that training satisfaction has a significant effect on work engagement and also research conducted by Hidayat (2018) which states that there is an effect of pay satisfaction on work engagement.

However, performance appraisal satisfaction has no effect on work engagement. So, this study is not in accordance with the results of Memon et al (2020) which state that performance appraisal satisfaction has a significant effect on work engagement. Furthermore, work engagement mediates the relationship between training satisfaction which also stated by Sari et al (2021). And also work engagement mediates the relationship between pay satisfaction and turnover intention therefore consistent with research conducted by Hidayat (2018) However, it did not have any mediating effect on performance appraisal satisfaction and turnover intention

which is not consistent with the study conducted by Memon et al. (2020).

The author is aware that in this study there are still some limitations in conducting this study. The limitations that exist in this study are:

First, the variables studied were only limited to training satisfaction, performance appraisal satisfaction, pay satisfaction, work engagement, and turnover intention. Second limitation is that the authors have not found and have not obtained many reference sources regarding the variables studied because there is still few research related to this matter. The third limitation is that the sample used is very limited. Research only focuses on employees from one company, which may not be representative to another population and sector.

Considering these limitations, the study has several recommendations and suggestions for further researcher:

The future researchers can further examine and analyze how much influence training satisfaction, performance appraisal satisfaction, pay satisfaction, and work engagement have on employee turnover intention both simultaneously and partially, both of which are assisted by independent variables as well as by dependent variables that may be influenced by other variables from this research. Second, future researchers can use more references regarding the variables that have been studied so that they can produce research that is far better. Also, the further researchers may use different objects from what researchers are currently doing, as well as use a larger and more varied sample than the research that has been conducted.

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